

The Michaelis-Menten kinetics and errors in estimated reaction constants : A reappraisal[†]

Sharmistha Dhatt and Kamal Bhattacharyya*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : pcsdhatt@gmail.com, pchemkb@gmail.com

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Abstract : Reaction constants in traditional Michaelis-Menten type enzyme kinetics are most often determined through a few linear plots. Such graphical plots sometimes provide reasonably good data. But, for a comparative survey, visual examinations are not enough. Instead, it is always advisable to go simultaneously for a few associated numerical tests. They can assess how far the measured values of the quantities sought are reliable, furnishing along with appropriate error estimates that can be checked against the corresponding non-linear methods. Here, we explicitly deal with a few such situations to stress the importance of these tests with specific examples. Also, we advocate a new scheme to mainly highlight how cases may appear with negative reaction constants and explore the origin of such bizarre findings. This exercise, in turn, might even judge the quality of the input data set and modify it to suit the needs. Pilot calculations bring the worth to light.

Keywords : Enzyme kinetics, Lineweaver-Burk type plots, negative reaction constants, reliability of kinetic data, data-set errors.

1. Introduction

An enzyme-catalyzed reaction is usually assumed to follow the Michaelis-Menten (MM)¹ mechanism, given by

Here, the substrate S combines with the enzyme E to form the complex C that subsequently yields the product P, regenerating the catalyst E. Denoting the concentrations of the species of interest by the corresponding small letters like s , e , c , etc., the relevant rate equations are obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} dc/dt &= k_1 e \cdot s - (k_{-1} + k_2)c; \\ V = dp/dt &= k_2 c. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Note that the rate of product formation V in (1) and the concentrations of all the species involved are actually time-dependent. In other words, $V = V(t)$, $c = c(t)$, etc. The initial conditions, viz., $s = s_0$ and $e =$

e_0 at $t = 0$, allow us to write the following two conservation equations, in addition to (1), for completeness of the problem :

$$\begin{aligned} e_0 &= e + c, \\ s_0 &= s + c + p. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

All other rate equations, i.e., expressions for de/dt and ds/dt , follow from (1) and (2). From experiments, however, it is not easy to estimate the individual rate constants like k_1 , k_{-1} or k_2 in (1). Instead, one finds that two characteristic *reaction constants*, defined by

$$V_m = k_2 e_0, \quad K_m = (k_{-1} + k_2)/k_1, \quad (3)$$

are obtainable. They turn out to be really important too in *all* discussions of enzyme kinetics¹⁻³. In (3), V_m signifies the *maximum* possible rate assuming, of course, that $e_0 \leq s_0$, while K_m stands for the Michaelis constant. If $e_0 \geq s_0$ is obeyed, V_m still remains a constant, but the maximum possible rate will then be given by $k_2 s_0$. The governing equation connecting

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rate and these reaction constants is usually written as (see later for justifications)

$$V = \frac{V_m s}{K_m + s} \quad (4)$$

Considerable attention has therefore been paid on (4) over the years. Several linearized versions of (4) have also appeared to simplify the task of obtaining V_m and K_m . However, these are often beset with problems like the accuracy of such linear plots²⁻⁶ in estimating the reaction constants, the reasons behind their deviations from linearity⁷, their comparative performances^{8,9}, etc. In this respect, a few instructive educational notes¹⁰ are also available.

It is easy to notice that (4) may be rearranged for linearity in a number of ways. Of these, a few relevant ones are as follows : First, we have the Hanes-Woolf (HW)¹¹ method, where sV^{-1} is plotted against s . The Lineweaver-Burk (LB) plot¹² comes second, which recommends a plot of V^{-1} vs. s^{-1} . The third scheme refers to a plot of V vs. Vs^{-1} and it is the Eadie-Hofstee (EH)¹³ proposal. We summarize these rearrangements below :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{HW : } \frac{s}{V} &= \frac{K_m}{V_m} + \frac{s}{V_m} \\ \text{LB : } \frac{1}{V} &= \frac{K_m}{V_m s} + \frac{1}{V_m} \\ \text{EH : } V &= V_m - \frac{VK_m}{s} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

With time, however, it has been noted that the LB method received the most attention¹. Indeed, the LB scheme still remains a premier tool in various studies on enzymatic reactions¹⁴ though some authors strongly disagree^{4,8,9}. Hence, the endeavor to somehow extract good reaction constants is continuing^{15,16}. The problem is thus an open one.

One important reason behind the observed disparity among the values of reaction constants obtained

by various means is, of course, the rather *uncritical* use of (4). Therefore, before proceeding further, we should pay some attention to the arrival of (4) from the basic eqs. (1) and (2). First, let us concentrate on the time $t = \tau$ at which the rate of reaction is *maximum*. Suppose, this occurs at a definite $c = \bar{c}$, corresponding to the maximum attainable value of c [$\bar{c} \leq \min(s_0, e_0)$] for specific values of the rate constants and the initial conditions, that ensures

$$dc/dt = 0, t = \tau. \quad (6)$$

For convenience, the concentrations of other relevant species at this time ($t = \tau$) may be denoted by \bar{e} , \bar{s} etc. Condition (6) is the most general one. Putting this condition in (1), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} k_1 \bar{e} \cdot \bar{s} - (k_{-1} + k_2) \bar{c} &= 0; \\ \bar{V} &= k_2 \bar{c}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Using the conservation for e_0 in (2), one finds from (7) the *exact* equation

$$\bar{V} = \frac{V_m \bar{s}}{K_m + \bar{s}}; t = \tau. \quad (8)$$

This equation looks precisely like (4). The lesson, therefore, is that (4) should strictly be used *only* at $t = \tau$. Notably, (8) does not demand one to invoke the steady-state approximation (SSA). Secondly, if the SSA holds over a time span, this implies that, in place of (6), we have

$$dc/dt \approx 0, \tau_1 \leq t \leq \tau_2. \quad (9)$$

Thus, over a range of time, the complex concentration, and hence the rate, remains *almost* constant at $V(t) \approx \bar{V}$ though s may considerably deviate from s_0 . Here, we have the better (see below) option of employing $V(t)$ and the *corresponding* $s(t)$ in (4). Thirdly, the most popular version of (4) reads as

$$V = \frac{V_m s_0}{K_m + s_0}. \quad (10)$$

It involves, apart from the SSA, further approximations like $e_0 \ll s_0$ and $\bar{c}^2 \approx 0$. The significance of V

in (10) is just its *virtual* constancy, and *no reference to time* is explicit here. In essence, therefore, the key eq. (10) rests on the following assumptions : (i) The SSA is valid. (ii) The time τ_2 is small enough to ensure that $\bar{p} \rightarrow 0$. (iii) The condition $e_0 \ll s_0$ is maintained. (iv) The stipulation $\bar{c}^2 \approx 0$ holds. (v) Finally, we need to also guarantee that the measured rate is *almost constant* within the concerned ($\tau_1 \leq t \leq \tau_2$) time interval. We shall see, if one disregards the above constraints in the course of employing (4), or any of its linearized versions appearing in (5), consequences may be dangerous.

A critical survey of the relevant literature²⁻¹⁰ reveals that discussions on the following points are still lacking : (i) How do the HW, LB and EH methods theoretically compare? How far does the nonlinear fitting procedure involving (4) fare over the conventional linear exercises based on (5)? Is there any *quantitative* measure? (ii) Is there any *other* alternative to the nonlinear fitting? (iii) Why does one sometimes find *negative* reaction constants and when? (iv) How should one ensure the *quality* of data set being handled? Is there a way to improve it?

In what follows, we like to take up the above issues for clarifications. Obviously, our attention will be paid to numerical procedures, not to the drawing of the plots or their *visual* deviations from linearity.

2. Experimental

2.1. The numerical experiments

The set of coupled nonlinear differential equations that follows from (1) and (2) is solved stepwise via the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method¹⁷. The stability of the numerical experiment is checked against the satisfaction of conservations in (2). The time step has been fixed at 10^{-6} min. We start with $s_0 = 10 \mu\text{ mol}$ and follow the dynamics up to 20 min. This is one *run*. Then, gradually, s_0 is increased in steps of 10 units. Six such runs are performed to prepare a set at each of two fixed e_0 (one at $1 \mu\text{ mol}$ and the other at $0.1 \mu\text{ mol}$) values and the results are recorded.

2.1.1. Choice of rate constants

To explore the relative performances, we need to choose the sets rather judiciously. In the present case, the rate constants are taken as $k_1 = 10.8 \mu\text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, $k_{-1} = 10.0 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $k_2 = 0.8 \text{ min}^{-1}$ ¹⁸. Thus, when we fix e_0 at $1 \mu\text{ mol}$, $V_m = 0.8 \mu\text{ mol min}^{-1}$ and $K_m = 1.0 \mu\text{ mol}$ follow. These *exact* values will later be compared against the findings from different schemes. Henceforth, we shall continue with the corresponding units for other quantities, but may not explicitly refer to them, for brevity. Notably, the above choice of the rate constants has been known¹⁸ to lead often to *marked errors* in estimated K_m , in particular. So, we felt obliged to consider such values for exploration.

2.1.2. The sets

It has already been remarked that one should actually use \bar{V} and \bar{s} in places of bare V and s in (4). This forms the ideal set. This is the set at $t = \tau$. The next worse alternative is to employ $V(t)$ and the *corresponding* $s(t)$, without checking the restriction of constancy of the former (at SSA). This class is represented also by sets A. However, provided that the conditions listed below (10) are obeyed, we may employ s_0 in (4) for s . Thus, we have *another set* (set B) at hand for every set A.

2.2. The methods

2.2.1. Linear methods

Here, the left side of (5) is fitted via a least squares method (LSM) as a function of the variable at the right side. The calculated slope and intercept then yield the reaction constants in (3). This is most popular numerical scheme for any of the (HW, LB or EH) methods. However, the plain graphical approach does not offer any quantitative estimate of error. Theoretically, an *overall measure* of error for the calculated V_m and K_m may be found from the expression

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \left| V_j - \left(\frac{V_m s_j}{K_m + s_j} \right) \right| \quad (11)$$

where M observations form a set. Thus, (11) offers a way of judging the comparative performances of the HW, LB and EH procedures via numerical means.

In view of the widespread belief that SSA is better obeyed with larger s_0 , reducing, as a consequence, the corresponding V^{-1} to be employed in LB calculations, it has been suggested that a better strategy specifically for LB would be to employ a *weighted* LB (WLB) method where V^4 acts as the weight factor⁶. Here, the graphical approach does not help. But, one may carry out the procedure in the same manner as the plain LSM. Only, the averages are computed with the weight factors. It is also recommended as a close alternative⁶ to the nonlinear fit (NLF) method. Having obtained the values of V_m and K_m via this scheme, one may again stick to (11) for finding the overall error involved.

2.2.2. The nonlinear method

As the next option, one may go for a NLF of data. In this scheme, one tries to minimize the error ε in (11) by choosing suitable V_m and K_m . It may be accomplished as follows. (i) Start from some arbitrary K_m . Calculate the two average values N and D , defined by

$$N = \langle V \rangle, D = \langle s / (K_m + s) \rangle, \quad (12)$$

to obtain V_m as $V_m = N/D$. (ii) Allow random variations of V_m around this value to find a minimum value for ε . (iii) Save the values of ε , V_m and K_m . (iv) Change K_m systematically in both directions to repeat steps (i) to (ii) and, only if the new ε is *less* than the previous minimum, proceed to step (iii). The recipe will finally yield a minimum ε along with the *optimal* V_m and K_m .

2.2.3. A new alternative

Keeping aside schemes like the LSM or NLF, there is another possibility to get the reaction constants within the MM framework. It does not seem to have been explored at all. In a set, we have M points (V_j, s_j) . Consider, for example the case with $i=1, j=2$. Us-

ing (4), one can solve for the two unknowns from this pair to obtain the results

$$V_m(1,2) = \frac{s_2 - s_1}{s_2/V_2 - s_1/V_1};$$

$$V_m(1,2) \left(\frac{1}{V_1} - \frac{1}{V_2} \right) = K_m(1,2) \left(\frac{1}{s_1} - \frac{1}{s_2} \right). \quad (13)$$

If a set is arranged in order of increasing s and V , we notice from the second expression in (13) that $V_m(i,j)/K_m(i,j)$ is *always positive*. However, bare $V_m(i,j)$ is positive only when the restriction

$$s_j/s_i > V_j/V_i, j > i, \quad (14)$$

is maintained. Otherwise, both V_m and K_m become *negative*. We shall see later the emergence of such a situation. For the points $(V_j, s_j), j = 1, 2, \dots, M$, one will get $M(M-1)/2$ values of V_m and K_m on applying (13) in a pair wise manner. We call it the pair wise solution (PS) scheme. The results for V_m and K_m may be separately averaged, obtaining along with their standard deviations (δV_m and δK_m). This PS scheme thus offers, very *unlike* the other schemes sketched earlier, *independent* errors of the reaction constants.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Validity of the steady-state approximation

Given the rate constants and initial conditions, it is not always transparent how one could ensure the validity of the SSA within the MM framework. Various criteria have been put forward from time to time. The adequacy of such riders, along with a number of fresh ones, has been tested elsewhere¹⁹ quite elaborately for closed systems. The case of open systems, however, is entirely different²⁰. Concerning the present study, we display the dynamics for a few runs in Fig. 1. It is pretty clear that the SSA is *not always* obeyed. The choice is deliberate, but is required to show the intricacies of the schemes in vogue. Clearly, the SSA is worst for the case of s_0 equal to 10 units and is best when $s_0 = 60$. Fig. 2 shows the temporal profiles of

Fig. 1. A plot of the temporal behavior of the calculated rate, showing that the SSA is not maintained at lower s_0 . Runs are conducted at $e_0 = 1.0$ and the rate constants are given in Sec. 2.1.1.

Fig. 2. Temporal profile of the relative substrate concentration at $e_0 = 1.0$ that shows the failure of the reactant stationary approximation.

these runs for the relative substrate concentration s/s_0 . Notably, the ‘reactant stationary approximation’ (RSA)¹⁸ is not valid for any run, though SSA is respected at least for the run with $s_0 = 60$.

3.2. Use of exact data

In Table 1, we display the first set of relevant results for our study. Here, the time $t = \tau$ refers to the maximum point of the rate-vs.-time plot, *i.e.*, where $(dv/dt)=0$. Hence, (6) and (8) are exactly obeyed. For this set, we take $e_0 = 1.0$. We find everywhere $\tau \ll 1$ min. No approximation is made anywhere on the computed data too (correct up to 14–15 decimal

Table 1. Exact results of runs with rates V at times $t = \tau$ and the corresponding substrate concentrations starting from varying initial substrate concentrations (in μ mol) s_0 at a fixed e_0 equal to 1 μ mol. The time $t = \tau$ refers to the maximum point of the rate-vs.-time plot, *i.e.*, where $V(t)$ is maximum; corresponding s values at τ are also tabulated

s_0	$t = \tau$	
	s	V
10.0	9.040986588168579	0.720344622657550
20.0	19.01538836571947	0.760023566573087
30.0	29.00473769964218	0.773337937185753
40.0	38.99558317935295	0.779998670263430
50.0	48.99791693764029	0.783999727616150
60.0	58.99427138294789	0.786665660507531

places). This, therefore, forms the *best set* and it should be considered for an *ideal study*.

Results of the above set are presented in Table 2. It is particularly comforting to note that *all the three linear methods* based on LSM perform *almost comparably* with the NLF scheme. We also notice that estimated V_m is much less susceptible to errors than K_m . This particular feature is retained in all the studies to follow. The moral is clear. If we use near-exact

Table 2. Results of employing the LSM *vs.* the NLF method to obtain V_m and K_m using the best set of data displayed in Table 1

Method	V_M	K_M	ϵ
EH	0.799 993	0.999 723	3.92 E-06
HW	0.799 999	0.999 924	4.04 E-06
LB	0.799 993	0.999 713	3.93 E-06
NLF	0.799 995	0.999 700	3.22 E-06
Exact	0.8	1.0	–

data for (\bar{s}, \bar{V}) in (4), good estimates are really obtained via any one of the linear schemes. The above assertion is true irrespective of whether the SSA or the RSA is obeyed or not. Moreover, the use of NLF may not offer any extra advantage in such situations.

3.3. Use of approximate data

Trouble arises when we approximate the data set by truncation. In Table 3, we display sample results for our computed data. From the data for different

Table 3. Results of runs at different times with varying initial substrate concentrations (in μ mol) s_0 at a fixed $e_0 = 1 \mu$ mol. The rate V at a certain time t and the substrate concentration at that instant s are displayed, along with s_0 for the specific run. The sets are numbered and the values are truncated

s_0	$t = \tau$ (1A)		$t = 5$ m (2A)		$t = 10$ m (3A)		$t = 20$ m (4A)	
	s	V	s	V	s	V	s	V
10.0	9.04	0.720	5.64	0.680	2.58	0.578	0.09	0.066
20.0	19.02	0.760	15.29	0.751	11.58	0.736	4.61	0.658
30.0	29.00	0.773	25.18	0.769	21.35	0.764	13.81	0.746
40.0	39.00	0.780	35.13	0.778	31.26	0.775	23.55	0.767
50.0	49.00	0.784	45.11	0.783	41.20	0.781	33.41	0.777
60.0	58.99	0.787	55.09	0.786	51.16	0.785	43.33	0.782

runs summarized in Table 3, the following sets may be considered for study : (i) set of values (truncated) for (\bar{s}, \bar{V}) at $t = \tau$ [to be called set 1A]; (ii) set of values for (s_0, \bar{V}) that is more traditional [to be called set 1B]; (iii) set of values for (s, V) where $V(t)$ and $s(t)$ are measured at $t \gg \tau$ [sets 2A – 4A]; (iv) set of values for (s_0, V) where $V(t)$ is *assumed* constant and measured at $t \gg \tau$ [to be called sets 2B – 4B]. All these 8 sets are then employed to extract values of V_m and K_m by employing the linear schemes mentioned above. For consistency, we take s and V correct up to 2 and 3 decimal places, respectively, and report the reaction constants up to 3 decimal places or 4 digits, as appropriate.

3.3.1. Performance of linear methods

Results from the sets in Table 3 are displayed in Table 4. All the three LSM-based strategies, *viz.*, the

EH, HW and LB, are employed everywhere and the overall errors are noted. For comparative purposes, such calculated errors are far superior and more quantitative than those found from visual plots. Note that the performance is best for set 1A, as expected. Calculated ϵ values reflect that set 4B is not just the worst one; here, we first encounter *negative reaction constants* as well. Besides, there is a gradual rise in ϵ as t increases. The error also rises in going from set A to set B. As experienced earlier, V_m is again found to be *more robust* than K_m under any circumstances. An added point is, the HW scheme usually overestimates K_m . We also notice that the use of $s(t)$ and the corresponding $V(t)$, even if $t \gg \tau$ (*e.g.*, at $t = 20$ min), do not seem to cause very serious errors in (4) or (5), provided we measure $s(t)$ and $V(t)$ for *all runs at the same t*. This is reflected from the observed *much better* performance of set 4A than set 4B.

Table 4. Employment of the LSM to obtain V_m and K_m from the data sets given in Table 3. Sets A employ the actual values of s at the times of rate (V) measurements, while sets B rely on the more traditional choice of s_0 in place of s . The sets are numbered in order of increasing time. Absolute error (ϵ) in each case reveals the adequacy

Set	Method								
	EH			HW			LB		
	V_m	K_m	ϵ	V_m	K_m	ϵ	V_m	K_m	ϵ
1A	0.800	1.007	1.25 E-04	0.800	1.015	2.16 E-04	0.800	1.007	1.24 E-04
2A	0.800	0.996	2.10 E-04	0.800	1.007	2.97 E-04	0.800	0.996	2.10 E-04
3A	0.800	0.990	2.87 E-04	0.800	1.005	5.46 E-04	0.800	0.990	2.80 E-04
4A	0.800	1.001	2.36 E-04	0.800	1.001	2.19 E-04	0.800	1.001	2.46 E-04
1B	0.802	1.135	3.39 E-04	0.802	1.116	3.77 E-04	0.802	1.136	3.40 E-04
2B	0.816	1.935	3.33 E-03	0.810	1.703	3.71 E-03	0.816	1.955	3.36 E-03
3B	0.863	4.503	1.51 E-02	0.836	3.440	1.55 E-02	0.871	4.809	1.58 E-02
4B	0.341	-15.59	4.02 E-01	-1.345	-128.1	2.39 E-01	-0.314	-52.49	1.64 E-00

Table 5. Magnifications in percentage errors at large times (set 4) for the various linear schemes owing to the replacement of the actual values of s (set 4A) by s_0 (set 4B)

Property	Method	Set	
		4A	4B
V_m	EH	0.02	57.32
	HW	0.01	268.18
	LB	0.03	139.19
K_m	EH	0.10	1658.54
	HW	0.06	12913.70
	LB	0.12	5349.23

3.3.2. Primary sources of errors

The first source of error lies in the lack of respect for set 1A. One may next opt for set 1B if measurements of $s(t)$ become troublesome. At large times,

Fig. 3. Plots showing a significant reduction of percentage error in substituting s_0 for s at $t = 20$ min when the condition $e_0 \ll s_0$ is obeyed. The ordinate is in the logarithmic scale.

situations change. Concentrating only on the sets 4A and 4B, we display in Table 5 how the calculated percent errors for the two reaction constants behave

wildly once we replace s by s_0 . A good reason that explains the discrepancy is the following. If $e_0 \ll s_0$ is not obeyed, SSA fails to hold. So, after a pretty long time ($\tau \ll t = 20$), $s(t)$ will differ significantly from s_0 . Had e_0 been further reduced from 1.0 to 0.1, keeping s_0 -values for the sets unchanged, the SSA would have been obeyed for all the runs (see Table 11 later). As a consequence, the errors incurred by the substitution of s_0 for $s(t)$ is much more serious at higher e_0 , our current case of concern. Fig. 3 reveals it quite transparently; here, we show the percent errors for the said substitution in two cases.

3.3.3. Performance of the nonlinear method

The real advantage of going over to NLF is clear once we compare the absolute errors in Table 4 with those in Table 6. Particularly, in respect of set 4B, considerable betterment has been achieved by adopting the NLF procedure. The *negative results* have all disappeared now. The absolute error has decreased significantly. A sane value for V_m has emerged, though K_m is not quite good. Therefore, when we deal specifically with a *poor set of data*, we need to *definitely* implement the NLF and check the outcomes against the LSM.

3.3.4. The weighted LB method

By now, it is clear that the set 1A is the best and 4B is the worst among all those given in Table 3. So, for brevity, we may discuss about these sets only. In order to additionally note the importance of the replacement of s_0 for $s(t)$, one may include sets 1B and 4A. Results of employing the WLB scheme on these sets are shown in Table 7. It is comforting to observe

Table 6. Results of applying the NLF method on all the sets displayed in Table 4 for the various linear schemes. Absolute error (ϵ) in each case reveals the worth

Set	NLF			Set	NLF		
	V_m	K_m	ϵ		V_m	K_m	ϵ
1A	0.800	1.006	1.15 E-04	1B	0.802	1.143	3.14 E-04
2A	0.800	0.996	1.89 E-04	2B	0.817	2.019	3.19 E-03
3A	0.800	0.989	2.69 E-04	3B	0.872	4.992	1.50 E-02
4A	0.800	0.995	2.18 E-04	4B	0.884	6.855	8.48 E-02

Table 7. Results of employing the WLB prescription on the extreme sets 1 and 4

Set	V_m	K_m	ε
1A	0.800	1.009	1.47 E-04
4A	0.800	0.999	2.26 E-04
1B	0.802	1.124	3.58 E-04
4B	0.837	3.885	9.89 E-02

that the negative results have *again disappeared* from set 4B. Moreover, the error is close to the NLF method and the values found are quite good; indeed, a much better K_m is found. Thus, the WLB procedure shows that it can also compete with the NLF method when we deal with a *very poor* data set. One may find additionally that the NLF fares only marginally than the WLB in terms of ε , as had been rightly pointed out elsewhere⁶.

3.3.5. Performance of our scheme

While we have noted the suitability of a few well-known schemes already in vogue, it is still not clear *why* the plain linear schemes have mostly (except for V_m by the EH method; see Table 4) yielded negative reaction constants for the set 4B. Another problem is that the goodness of computed V_m or K_m could not be separately gauged; one could at most obtain an *overall* error ε . We need to explore as well whether there exists any simple alternative to the linear schemes that can assess *a priori* the goodness of a chosen

input data set and try to *modify* it. These issues will concern us right now.

3.3.5.1. The emergence of negative reaction constants

Results of the PS scheme, outlined in Sec. 2.2.3, are first shown for the set 1A in Table 8. As expected, scatter in the estimated values of either $V_m(i, j)$ or $K_m(i, j)$ is little in case 1A. It is also important to witness that $V_m(i, j)$ values differ from the exact V_m (equal to 0.8) only in the third decimal place, if at all, while the $K_m(i, j)$ data are mostly affected from true value at the second decimal place. Thus, we again notice the *relative robustness* of V_m in comparison with K_m . However, when this very scheme is applied to set 4B, the values behave wildly, as Table 9 reveals. Particularly, *negative values* show up in the *entire* first row. We now know that the origin lies in the *violation* of condition (14). Note also that the scatter is still much less for V_m in comparison with K_m . Therefore, this becomes a general feature; measured K_m is always more susceptible to error, specifically when we try to simplify (4) by (10).

3.3.5.2. Goodness of individual reaction constant

As indicated earlier, the PS scheme yields 15 ($6 \times 5 / 2$) different values for either V_m or K_m for a set of 6 members. These values can be averaged. They should

Table 8. Results of adopting the PS scheme on set 1A. The upper and lower entries display values of V_m and K_m , respectively

	2	3	4	5	6
1	0.800 1.008	0.800 1.000	0.800 1.006	0.800 1.006	0.800 1.010
2		0.799 0.977	0.800 1.002	0.800 1.002	0.801 1.014
3			0.801 1.052	0.801 1.032	0.801 1.052
4				0.8 1.0	0.801 1.051
5					0.802 1.128

Table 9. Results of adopting the PS scheme on set 4B. The upper and lower entries display values of V_m and K_m , respectively

	2	3	4	5	6
1	-0.083 -22.510	-0.180 -37.226	-0.302 -55.746	-0.459 -79.530	-0.669 -111.295
2		1.018 10.954	0.919 7.942	0.884 6.855	0.863 6.242
3			0.838 3.690	0.829 3.324	0.822 3.042
4				0.820 2.751	0.814 2.442
5					0.808 1.995

be ideally called \bar{V}_m and \bar{K}_m , but we shall call them plainly as V_m or K_m for the sake of brevity, unless specific need arises. The standard deviation (SD) can be calculated as well. In Table 10, we summarize a few findings. Since the averaging procedure is quite different in the LSM from the PS scheme, the effects differ. In fact, the averaging via LSM in cases of EH, HW and LB schemes are all very dissimilar. As a result, data found for PS in Table 10 upon averaging do not have any parallel in the EH, HW or LB calculations (see Table 4). However, this table tells us *first* about the *sanctity* of the individual estimated values. If the SD values are termed as δV_m and δK_m , we should theoretically have $\delta V_m \ll |\bar{V}_m|$ and $\delta K_m \ll |\bar{K}_m|$. Even *modest* estimates should satisfy $\delta V_m/|\bar{V}_m| < 0.1$ and $\delta K_m/|\bar{K}_m| < 0.1$. Note that, in this respect, set 4B is miserable. The scatters are such severe that V_m can lie anywhere within 0.462 ± 0.580 and K_m within -17.138 ± 36.172 . Table 10 thus also furnishes *separate error estimate* for each of the two reaction constants. As an alternative, one may look for the overall error ε here too by putting these average estimates in (11). But, we do not intend to assess it here.

3.3.5.3. Reliability of input data

We have learnt from the discussion above, along with Tables 4, 6 and 10, that sets 1A to 4A and 1B to 4B are progressively worse in respect of calculations of the reaction constants. Indeed, the PS scheme alone tells us nicely about the quality of a set. A reliable set should obey the conditions $\delta V_m \ll |\bar{V}_m|$ and

Table 10. Average values of reaction constants along with their SD values obtained from the PS scheme are displayed for selected sets

Set	V_m	δV_m	K_m	δK_m
1A	0.800	6.81 E-04	1.023	3.53 E-02
4A	0.800	7.44 E-04	1.002	2.42 E-02
1B	0.802	1.02 E-03	1.111	3.77 E-02
4B	0.462	5.80 E-01	-17.138	36.172

$\delta K_m \ll |\bar{K}_m|$. In other words, *goodness of a set* may be judged on the basis of the PS tables. For example, one can conclude safely from Tables 9 and 10 that the set 4B should not be employed in calculating K_m and V_m by any method. This is a definite advantage to be exploited in the next subsection.

At lower e_0 , the SSA is satisfied in a much better way. Hence, the replacement of s by s_0 is not that serious (cf. Fig. 3). Table 11 shows, how the disastrous situation for set 4B can be avoided by using $e_0 = 0.1$ in the runs.

3.3.5.4. A route to modify the data set

A glance at Table 9 would convince one that the most undesirable (negative) results follow only when the PS involves $i = 1$ (row 1). This is not unexpected in view of the largest deviation from SSA shown in Fig. 1 for the case of $s_0 = 10$, the first member of any set. Indeed, this causes a big difference between $s(t)$ and s_0 , which is responsible for the violation of (14). Once we are certain about this fact, we can remove this run to form a modified set for considerable consistency. In Table 12, relevant results are

Table 11. Results of runs at $t = 20$ min with varying initial substrate concentrations (in μ mol) s_0 at a fixed $e_0 = 0.1 \mu$ mol. The rate $V(t)$ and $s(t)$ are displayed. Exact values are : $V_m = 0.08$, $K_m = 1.0$. Comparing the outcomes with set 4B, the need for satisfaction of the SSA is obvious. Errors ε for others and SD values for PS scheme are shown

s_0	s	V	Method	V_m	K_m	Error
10.0	8.47	0.072	EH	0.080	1.126	1.95 E-04
20.0	18.38	0.076	HW	0.080	1.192	2.43 E-04
30.0	28.36	0.077	LB	0.080	1.126	1.95 E-04
40.0	38.34	0.078	WLB	0.080	1.140	1.97 E-04
50.0	48.33	0.078	NLF	0.080	1.143	1.83 E-04
60.0	58.33	0.079	PS	0.080	1.303	0.001, 0.839

Table 12. Results of the reaction constants obtained by using various methods, with the corresponding errors, for the modified set 4B with the rate for $s_0 = 10$ dropped. In the PS scheme, individual SD is recorded

Method	V_m	K_m	Error
EH	0.875	6.090	1.08 E-02
HW	0.856	5.178	1.08 E-02
LB	0.881	6.405	1.10 E-02
WLB	0.837	3.885	1.13 E-02
NLF	0.884	6.855	1.01 E-02
PS	0.861	4.924	0.062, 2.793

noted. One may appreciate that, although errors are still sizeable, the values do not differ much in moving from one method to the other. Results in Tables 4, 6, 7 and 10 for the *parent set* 4B lend credence to this observation.

3.3.5.5. Analysis of some other data

A thorough statistical comparison among several linear transformations of (4) had earlier been made⁸ after introducing different kinds of errors in data through computer programs. These authors have also noted the appearance of negative reaction constants from the LB scheme when specific types of errors are incorporated. The parent set is given in Table 13. We have found that the results obtained from various methods are very similar in character. This again confirms our previous assertion (see Tables 1 and 2) that, if the right set of data is taken, results are virtually independent of the chosen scheme.

Another exhaustive statistical analysis⁴ used data

Table 13. A set has been taken from an earlier work⁸ to show the performances of various methods under scrutiny.

Exact values are : $V_m = 30$, $K_m = 15$. Errors ϵ for others and SD values for the PS scheme are shown. The WLB scheme performs almost comparably with the NLF one, and hence not displayed

s	V	Method	V_m	K_m	Error
2.5	4.29	EH	29.98	14.98	3.27 E-03
5.0	7.5	HW	30.00	14.99	2.58 E-03
10.0	12.0	LB	29.95	14.96	5.57 E-03
20.0	17.14	NLF	30.00	15.00	1.69 E-03
40.0	21.82	PS	29.97	14.97	0.063, 0.044

of the substrate *nicotinamide mononucleotide*²¹ at pH 4.95. Here, however, the situation is quite weak. We show in Table 14 the parent data set and results derived via the schemes discussed so far. One notes that only the HW and WLB methods come close to the provisional values. Even the NLF scheme performs

Table 14. Enzyme kinetics data for the reaction of *nicotinamide mononucleotide*²¹ at pH 4.95, and performances of various methods under scrutiny. Provisional values are $V_m = 0.679$, $K_m = 0.569$. Errors ϵ for others and SD values for the PS scheme are shown

s	V	Method	V_m	K_m	Error
0.138	0.148	EH	0.626	0.490	1.27 E-02
0.220	0.171	HW	0.685	0.582	9.24 E-03
0.291	0.234	LB	0.585	0.441	1.65 E-02
0.560	0.324	WLB	0.680	0.571	9.27 E-03
0.766	0.390	NLF	0.696	0.601	8.70 E-03
1.460	0.493	PS	0.491	0.358	0.592, 0.754

poorly. This calls for a thorough scrutiny, and we like to highlight the PS scheme at this juncture. Results show considerable SD for either property, larger than the individual averages. So, we proceed further to examine the data in PS Table 15. It immediately shows some problems with the *second* row due to the appearance of negative values. Thus, the chosen set itself has problems with $i = 2$. Therefore, we again modify this set by deleting the second (s , V) entry from Table 14. Analysis of this fresh set brings to

Table 15. Results of adopting the PS scheme on the set displayed in Table 14. The upper and lower entries exhibit values of V_m and K_m , respectively

	2	3	4	5	6
1	0.232	0.492	0.530	0.609	0.652
	0.078	0.320	0.356	0.430	0.470
2		-1.653	0.770	0.806	0.740
		-2.346	0.770	0.817	0.732
3			0.555	0.659	0.680
			0.399	0.529	0.555
4				0.874	0.730
				0.951	0.702
5					0.696
					0.601

light sufficiently better estimates. These data are compiled in Table 16. Note in particular the effects on $\delta V_m/|\bar{V}_m|$ and $\delta K_m/|\bar{K}_m|$ in the PS scheme by dropping the second entry (compare Table 14). The scatter is now much less as well. The advantage of introducing the PS is now quite apparent.

Table 16. Results obtained by removing the second member in the set displayed in Table 14. Errors ε for others and SD values for the PS scheme are shown

Method	V_m	K_m	Error
EH	0.623	0.463	9.97 E-03
HW	0.664	0.530	7.56 E-03
LB	0.592	0.421	1.30 E-02
WLB	0.666	0.538	7.08 E-03
NLF	0.680	0.555	6.95 E-03
PS	0.648	0.531	0.105, 0.178

4. Concluding remarks

In summary, we wished to first highlight the quantitative measure ε in (11) that showed the relative merits of both the linear and nonlinear schemes. Agreement of the values of estimated reaction constants among the various linear methods reflects the quality of a set. While the NLF procedure always fares over the conventional LSM-based numerical exercises, for very good-quality data sets (see, *e.g.*, Tables 1, 2 and 13), one need not invoke the NLF scheme. Therefore, the failure to obey the RSA is *not* the real reason for marked errors in estimated K_m , as is sometimes believed¹⁸. We found also that the WLB is almost a virtual alternative to the NLF⁶. Secondly, an altogether *different* kind of approach, the PS scheme, has been advocated here. It shows very clearly the goodness of a set and also why one sometimes finds *negative* reaction constants (see, *e.g.*, Tables 9 and 15), not just in the LB scheme²², but elsewhere too. An added advantage of this scheme is that, here individual errors in terms of the SD values for both K_m and V_m are found (see, *e.g.*, Tables 10–14 and 16). Finally, on the basis of the PS table introduced here, we demonstrated that it is not only possible to ensure the *quality* of data set being handled but also, in fa-

vorable situations, *modify* the set towards betterment. Two cases in point are our set 4B and the set in Table 14; both have thus been modified to gain advantage.

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Note added in proof :

The MM form given by eq. (4) with just two ‘effective’ reaction constants appears in a variety of contexts that are much more complex in character (see, *e.g.*, I. Barel and F. L. H. Brown, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2017, **146**, 014101, and references quoted therein). In all such cases, goodness of the estimated values of each such constant would pose similar problems as highlighted here.

References

1. K. A. Johnson and R. S. Goody, *Biochem.*, 2011, **50**, 8264.
2. S. Schnell and P. K. Maini, *Comments Theor. Biol.*, 2003, **8**, 169.
3. A. Cornish-Bowden, *Persp. Sci.*, 2015, **4**, 3.
4. G. N. Wilkinson, *Biochem. J.*, 1961, **80**, 324.
5. R. Eisenthal and A. Cornish-Bowden *Biochem. J.*, 1974, **139**, 715.
6. A. Cornish-Bowden, *J. Theor. Biol.*, 1991, **153**, 437.
7. P. C. Engel and W. Ferdinand, *Biochem. J.*, 1973, **131**, 97; L-H. Wang, M-S. Wang, X-A. Zeng, D-M. Gong and Y-B. Huang, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 2017, **1861**, 3189.
8. J. E. Dowd and D. S. Riggs, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1965, **240**, 863.
9. G. L. Atkins and I. A. Nimmo, *Biochem. J.*, 1975, **149**, 775.
10. N. C. Price, *Biochem. Edu.*, 1985, **13**, 81; R. J. Ritchie and T. Pravan, *Biochem. Edu.*, 1996, **24**, 196; J. K. Harper and E. C. Heider, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 2017, **94**, 610.
11. C. S. Hanes, *Biochem. J.*, 1932, **26**, 1406.
12. H. Lineweaver, D. Burk and W. E. Deming, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 225; H. Lineweaver and D. Burk, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 658.
13. G. S. Eadie, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1942, **146**, 85; B. H. J. Hofstee, *Science*, 1952, **116**, 329; B. H. J. Hofstee, *Nature*, 1959, **184**, 1296.

14. W. Liang, A. P. Fernandes, A. Holmgren, X. Li and L. Zhong, *FEBS*, 2016, **283**, 446.
15. W. Stroberg and S. Schnell, *Biophys. Chem.*, 2016, **219**, 17.
16. M. L. R. González, S. Cornell-Kennon, E. Schaefer and P. Kuzmič, *Anal. Biochem.*, 2017, **518**, 16.
17. W. H. Press, S. A. Teukolsky, W. T. Vetterling and B. P. Flannery, "Numerical Recipes : The Art of Scientific Computing", CUP, 3rd ed., 2007.
18. S. M. Hanson and S. Schnell, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2008, **112**, 8654; S. Schnell, *FEBS*, 2014, **281**, 464.
19. S. Dhatt and K. Bhattacharyya, *J. Math. Chem.*, 2013, **51**, 1467; K. Bhattacharyya and S. Dhatt, *MATCH Commun. Math. Comput. Chem.*, 2013, **70**, 759.
20. K. Banerjee and K. Bhattacharyya, *Chem. Phys.*, 2014, **438**, 1; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2015, **43**, 235102.
21. M. R. Atkinson, J. F. Jackson and R. K. Morton, *Biochem. J.*, 1961, **80**, 318.
22. S. Dhatt and K. Bhattacharyya, *ARXIV*, 1710.08131.